
APPRAISING THE OPERATIONAL PERFORMANCE OF ONNE PORT (A CASE STUDY)

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Abstracts

Onne Port is a major seaport located in Rivers State, Nigeria. The modern infrastructure and operational capabilities of Onne Port makes it a key player in the maritime sector; thus, providing easy access to the oil and gas resources of Nigeria. The aim of this paper is to appraise the operational performance of Onne Port. The objectives are; to determine the relationship between ship traffic and cargo throughput in Onne Port, and to determine the relationship between ship traffic and Gross Registered Tonnage (GRT) of Onne Port. The primary source of data was from the Onne Port Annual Statistical Report spanning from the years 2005 to 2020. Other sources of data include the Nigerian Ports Authority (NPA) Handbook, the National Bureau of Statistics, Nigeria (NBS), the Nigerian Maritime Administration and Safety Agency (NIMASA) Annual Reports, internet sources, interviews, and so on. Information that was extracted include but not limited to Cargo Throughput, Ship Turnaround Time, Gross Registered Tonnage (GRT), Berth Occupancy Rate, Operational Statistics Summary, Ship traffic, container traffic, and others. The research employed descriptive statistics to analyze and evaluate the mean and standard deviation of the variables. The research hypotheses were tested using inferential statistical tool of Pearson Product Moment Correlation and Factor Analysis Model. Data analysis revealed a significant positive correlation between ship traffic and other performance indicators like cargo throughput and ship gross registered tonnage of Onne Port. The implication of this is that increased ship traffic leads to higher cargo throughput, higher GRT and consequently increase in port revenue or operational performance of Onne Port. The research however, highlighted the need for operational efficiency and infrastructure optimization to meet evolving demands in the maritime industry.

Keywords: Cargo throughput, operational performance, Seaport, ship traffic, Gross Registered Tonnage (GRT)

1.0 Introduction

The Maritime Industry is one of the most lucrative industries in the world. It plays a major role in the economic development of any country by largely setting the pace for growth experienced in other industries. More than 80% of world trade is transported by sea; societies and businesses depend on the efficient clearance of vessels and goods in ports worldwide to function, develop, and prosper (Chilaka, 2022). A seaport is a facility on the coast or shore that provides berthing and cargo handling operations for ships, allowing for the loading and unloading of cargo, passengers, or both. Seaports play an extremely important role in a country's transportation system (Onokala and Chidinma, 2020). This is not only a place for ships to dock but also an important connection centre for transporting goods and people between different locations. More than simply a stopover, seaports are the heart of commercial and economic activity.

Conventionally, a port is defined as a transit area, a gateway through which goods and people move from and to the sea. It is a place of contact between the land and maritime space, a node where ocean and inland transport systems interact, and a place of convergence for different transportation modes. Ports are catalysts for economic development as they enable trade and support supply chains. Port investments have economic benefits that can be direct, indirect, or induced. These strategic hubs connect nations, industries, and communities, enabling the efficient movement of goods, services, and ideas across the globe.

Various types of ports exist viz:

1. Natural ports: Formed by natural harbors or bays.
2. Artificial ports: Man-made, constructed through land reclamation or dredging.
3. River ports: Located on rivers, handling inland waterway traffic.
4. Dry ports: Inland ports, connected to seaports via rail/road.

According to Iwhiwhu (2020), the various challenges facing seaports include congestion, infrastructure constraints, environmental concerns, security threats, digitalization and automation. Despite these challenges, the economic benefits of seaports extend beyond the immediate vicinity as seaports remain the engine of economic growth thus, generating significant revenue, employment, and investment opportunities. They handle approximately 90% of global trade, with cargo volumes exceeding 10 billion tons annually (Onwuegbuchunam and others, 2021). Nowadays, seaports perform numerous functions as compared to what they used to do decades ago. Seaports are vital to any manufacturer's supply chain plan. Along with this, seaports are ranked based on numerous aspects in today's time. Some of the aspects include the amount of automation equipment that they possess, their workforce skills, their access to key markets, berth occupancy rate, cargo throughput, turnaround time, dwell time and customer satisfaction (Pinwa, 2019).

1.1 Study Area: Onne Port

Onne Port Complex situated on the Bonny River Estuary along Ogu Creek is the first port of its kind in Nigeria that operated the Landlord Port Model devised to encourage private sector participation in the Port Industry. Strategically located, the Port is one of the largest Oil and Gas Free Zone in the world supporting exploration and production for Nigerian activities. The Free Zone provides a logistics Oil Service centre for the Oil and Gas Industry in Nigeria both Onshore and Offshore. It also provides easy access to the entire West African and Sub-Saharan Oil fields (Nigerian Ports Authority, 2022).

According to the National Bureau of Statistics, Nigeria (2017) Onne Port accounts for over 65% of the export cargo through the Nigerian Sea Port. There are multiple operations that are carried out in the Port in addition to the Oil and Gas operations. Some of such multiple

operations are General Cargoes, Bulk Cargoes (Dry & Wet), Oil Well Equipment, Containerized Cargoes and other Logistics Services provided to companies that are customers and tenants. Hence the Port is a multi-purpose Cargo Port. The Port is highly industrialized with modern facilities and equipment that can stand the test of time. There is also adequate land available for development to all customers and prospective investors who desire to partner with the Port in the Maritime Business. The Port covers an area of 2,538.115 hectares.

Onne Port has one of the biggest harbour mobile cranes in Africa (Liebherr 600) with a lifting capacity of 208 metric tons and 220 Gmk5220 grove twin cranes that has capacity of lifting single heavy cargo of 300 tons owned by one of the Terminal Operators in the Port. Also, safe and comfortable hospitality facilities are available for Oil & Gas clientele at the Free Zone / Port Area. The Port is on security level one (1) creating a safe, secure and customer friendly environment for business (Nigerian Maritime Administration and Safety Agency, 2024).

1.2 Aim of Study

The aim of the study is to appraise the operational performance of Onne Port in Nigeria.

1.3 Objectives of the Study

For this paper, the following research objectives were considered:

- i. To determine relationship between ship traffic and cargo throughput in Onne Port.
- ii. To determine the relationship between ship traffic and Gross Registered Tonnage (GRT) of Onne Port.

1.4 Research Questions

- i. Is there significant relationship between ship traffic and cargo throughput in Onne Port?
- ii. Is there significant relationship between ship traffic and Gross Registered Tonnage (GRT) of Onne Port?

1.5 Null Hypothesis

- i. **H₀₁:** There is no significant relationship between ship traffic and cargo throughput in Onne Port.
- ii. **H₀₂:** There is no significant relationship between ship traffic and Gross Registered Tonnage (GRT) of Onne Port.

2.0 Research Method

2.1 Source of Data Collection

The primary source of data was from the Onne Port Annual Statistical Report spanning from the years 2005 to 2020. Other sources of data include the Nigerian Ports Authority (NPA) Handbook, the National Bureau of Statistics, Nigeria (NBS), the Nigerian Maritime Administration and Safety Agency (NIMASA) Annual Reports, internet sources, interviews, and so on. Information that was extracted include but not limited to Cargo Throughput, Ship Turnaround Time, Gross Registered Tonnage (GRT) Berth Occupancy Rate, Operational Statistics Summary, Ship traffic, container traffic, and others.

2.2 Method of Data Analysis

This research employed descriptive statistics to analyze and evaluate the mean and standard deviation of the variables. The research hypotheses were tested using inferential statistical tool of Pearson Product Moment Correlation and Factor Analysis Model.

3.0 Data Analysis and Discussion

3.1 Data Presentation

Table 3.1: Operational Performance of Onne Port from 2005-2020

Year	Ship Traffic (i.e. number of ships) (ST)	Cargo Throughput (CTP) (Tones)	Gross Registered Tonnage (GRT)
2005	392	2,554,328	42,625,452
2006	402	1,582,037	32,910,753
2007	417	3,144,943	38,102,995
2008	417	2,482,177	27,092,386
2009	432	20,785,455	41,053,001
2010	619	20,921,727	40,198,219
2011	885	26,529,884	42,735,452
2012	858	27,462,017	42,900,753
2013	823	24,701,689	38,612,995
2014	865	27,968,869	43,482,386
2015	741	26,526,815	44,053,589
2016	659	23,458,883	40,091,365
2017	671	26,049,226	42,563,511
2018	662	26,609,140	42,273,178
2019	721	27,808,857	43,725,972
2020	695	27,898,423	42,472,148

Source: Onne Port Annual Statistical Report 2005-2020

3.2 Data Analysis

Table 3.2: Descriptive Statistics Analysis

	ST (Ship traffic)	CTP (Cargo throughput)	GRT (Gross registered tonnage)
Mean	14.880	52868008	1.34+08
Median	12.045	56354064	1.32+08
Maximum	72.800	84951927	1.91+08
Minimum	6.6000	13273053	788324
Std. Dev.	12.807	23699720	299413
Skewness	3.7685	-0.320473	0.0583
Kurtosis	17.502	1.670805	2.4798
Jarque-Bera	289.38	2.359035	0.307889
Probability	0.0000	0.307427	0.857319
Sum	386.89	1.37E+09	3.49E+09
Sum Sq. Dev.	4100.9	1.40E+16	2.24E+16
Observations	15	15	15

Source: SPSS 22 output

Table 3.3: Augmented Dickey-Fuller Test Results

Unit Root Test at Levels			
Variable	ADF Test Statistic	P-Value	Remark
CTP (Cargo throughput)	-1.148270	0.6790	Not stationary
GRT(Gross registered tonnage)	0.593336	0.9866	Not stationary
ST (Ship traffic)	-5.867181	0.0001	Stationary At (0)
Unit Root Test at 1st Difference			
Variable	ADF Test Statistic	P-Value	Remark
CTP (Cargo throughput)	-1.982177	0.2920	Not stationary
GRT(Gross registered tonnage)	-4.372770	0.0023	Stationary At (1)
ST (Ship traffic)	-7.133224	0.0000	Stationary At (1)
Unit Root Test At 2nd Difference			
Variable	ADF Test Statistic	P-Value	Remark
CTP (Cargo throughput)	-4.477839	0.0022	Stationary At (2)
GRT(Gross registered tonnage)	-5.785659	0.0001	Stationary At (2)
ST (Ship traffic)	-4.426635	0.0025	Stationary At (2)

Source: Augmented Dickey-Fuller Test Results computed by researcher

Table 3.4: Pearson Correlation Test

Covariance Analysis: Ordinary			
Sample: 2005 – 2020 Included observations: 15			
Correlation			
Probability	CTP	GRT	ST
CTP (Cargo throughput)	1.000000	0.461977	0.298528
GRT(Gross registered tonnage)	0.461977	1.000000	0.406444
ST (Ship traffic)	0.298528	0.406444	1.000000

Source: SPSS 22 output

Table 3.5: Regression Test

Dependent Variable: CTP		Method: Least Squares		
Sample: 2005 to 2020		Included observations: 15		
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
GRT (Gross registered tonnage)	-7.24E-05	4.35E-05	-1.664717	0.1108
ST (Ship traffic)	65.41100	84.48303	0.774250	0.4474
R-squared	0.943170	Mean dependent var		46848.75
Adjusted R-squared	0.932345	S.D. dependent var		18655.67
S.E. of regression	4852.448	Akaike info criterion		19.98340
Sum squared resid	4.94E+08	Schwarz criterion		20.22534
Log likelihood	-254.7841	Hannan-Quinn criteria		20.05307
F-statistic	87.13038	Durbin-Watson stat		1.505689
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000			

Source: E view test result

3.3 Discussion

3.3.1 Relationship between ship traffic and cargo throughput

The data analysis showed a positive correlation, indicating that there is a strong relationship between ship traffic and cargo throughput in Onne Port. The implication of this is that:

1. Increased ship traffic at Onne Port led to higher cargo throughput – more vessels calling at Onne Port result in higher cargo volumes.
2. Larger vessels at Onne Port also led to higher cargo throughput (that is, increased vessel size leads to higher cargo capacity).
3. Given the busy nature of Onne Port, more cargo and passenger activity at the port corresponds to higher cargo throughput.

The findings challenged the null hypothesis (H_0) and suggested that cargo throughput is a crucial factor influencing ship traffic in Onne Port. Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected and the alternative accepted.

3.3.2 Relationship between ship traffic and Gross Registered Tonnage

The data analysis also indicated a positive correlation with a significant relationship between ship traffic and Gross Registered Tonnage (GRT) at Onne Port. Reasons being that:

1. Increased ship traffic led to higher GRT: more vessels calling at Onne Port result in higher total GRT at the port.
2. Larger vessels calling at Onne Port led to higher GRT because increased vessel size leads to higher GRT.
3. The busy nature of Onne Ports led to higher GRT because more cargo and passenger activity at a port corresponds to higher GRT.

The regression analysis showing a highly significant positive relationship between Gross Registered Tonnage (GRT) and ship traffic suggest that the operational efficiency, as reflected in Gross Registered Tonnage (GRT), played a vital role in shaping the ship traffic at Onne port. Thus, the null hypothesis was rejected and the alternative accepted.

4.0 Conclusion

This study attempted to appraise the operational performance of Onne Port. The findings conclude that there exists positive correlation between ship traffic and other port performance indicators like cargo throughput and ship gross registered tonnage of Onne Port. Factors influencing the relationship include: vessel size and type, cargo volume and complexity, port infrastructure and capacity, trade patterns and economic conditions. However, the impact of this is that increased ship traffic leads to higher cargo throughput, higher GRT and consequently increase in port revenue or operational performance of Onne Port.

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